

Proposal of new safety measures for European Sodium Fast Reactor to be evaluated in framework of Horizon-2020 ESFR-SMART project

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Abstract

Following the previous European projects EFR and CP ESFR [1], a new Horizon-2020 project, called ESFR-SMART, was launched in September 2017 [2]. This project will consider the safety objectives envisaged for Generation-IV reactors and the update of European and international safety frameworks, taking into account the Fukushima accident. In accordance with these objectives, guidelines will be defined to drive ESFR-SMART developments, mainly simplifying the design and using all the positive features of the Sodium Fast Reactors (SFR), such as low coolant pressure; efficiency of natural convection; possibility of decay heat removal (DHR) by atmospheric air; high thermal inertia and long grace period before a human intervention is needed. In this paper, the safety objectives are presented in terms of defence-in-depth principle, extreme natural hazards to take into account, mitigation measures, *etc.* In this R&D framework, a set of new ambitious safety measures is introduced for further evaluation within the ESFR-SMART project. This proposed set aims at consistency with the main lines of safety evolutions since the Fukushima accident, but it does not yet constitute the final comprehensive safety analysis. This analysis will be done in the ESFR-SMART project to assess the relevance of the whole design in comparison to the final safety objectives. It should also be noted that some of these proposals are useful but could be replaced by other proposals in case of non-final validation. This first reassembly leads to a simplified reactor, forgiving and including a lot of passivity. This first version will be reinforced by the various tasks works in the forthcoming months.

1. Introduction

A conceptual design of the 1500 MWe European Sodium Fast Reactor was studied in the FP7 CP ESFR project [1]. It features an integrated reactor concept with six secondary loops. The Horizon-2020 EU ESFR-SMART project aims at proposing a fast neutron reactor using the sodium as coolant, with different safety improvements, in particular taking into account the safety objectives envisaged for Generation-IV reactors and the recommendations following the Fukushima accident.

The paper gives a first review of the safety measures proposed to enhance the ESFR safety. These safety measures integrated into a whole plant design reassembly will be assessed in more details during the next phases of the ESFR-SMART project. Finally the project will also recommend the additional R&D needed for implementation of the promising safety measures.

2. General safety objectives for Generation-IV SFRs

As an introduction, it is reminded that, despite a high level of core-meltdown prevention, mitigation provisions for this accident are adopted under the fourth level of defence in depth. In the event of a core-meltdown accident, the objective is to have very low radiological releases, and according to

current thresholds, such that no off-site measures have to be implemented. If measures are nevertheless needed (*e.g.* restrictions on the consumption of crops), these must be limited in time and space, with sufficient time for their implementation. The even-temporary evacuation of populations should not be necessary and only their sheltering, limited in time and space, would be possible.

For Generation-IV SFRs, a probabilistic objective of the core-meltdown accident prevention is proposed, with the same value as for Generation-III Pressurized Water Reactors (*i.e.*, a core damage frequency below 10^{-5} per reactor-year for all events including hazards, with considerations of uncertainties). An additional and prescriptive reduction of the core-meltdown probability is not justified and might be even counterproductive. Indeed, the current probabilistic objectives are already ambitious and at the edge of representativeness. *De facto*, the probabilistic objective hardening, for already highly unlikely events, could increase the plant and its operation complexity, and then reduce its everyday-life safety, for a marginal gain in terms of core-meltdown probability.

On the other hand, the effort for Generation-IV SFRs should focus on the demonstration of the verification of the objectives. In particular, for Generation-IV SFRs, for which limited experience feedback is available, the safety demonstration will rely primarily on deterministic methods so as to cover the defence-in-depth levels and to implement the core-meltdown-accident prevention and mitigation provisions. Probabilistic methods, whenever relevant, will provide an additional insight.

The Fukushima accident lessons have led to new guidelines so as to make the plant more robust against natural hazards:

- to ensure that sufficient design margins are available on the equipment necessary to avoid cliff edge effects in terms of off-site radiological consequences, for natural hazards more severe than those considered in the plant reference design domain;
- to favour a significant plant autonomy, regarding the amounts of time necessary for a possible external intervention;
- to promote the provisions enabling the implementation of internal or external means of intervention, on the site in a damaged state.

In general, the intended objectives are similar to those of the Generation-III PWR reactors. For Generation-IV SFRs, these lessons are considered from the design early stages, taking into account the concept specificities, for example by promoting passivity or autonomy. These and other measures for reactivity control are described in more detail in the following. For Generation-IV reactors the methodology of practical elimination is to be applied since the beginning of the design studies, to identify the severe accident situations that would not be mitigated under economically reasonable conditions, and to make them extremely unlikely rare with a high level of confidence through appropriate design and operating provisions.

3. Reminders of the SFR type-of-reactor assets and sensitive points

The document produced by IRSN for the 2014 Permanent Group [3] presents a review of the assets and of the sensitive points of each type of Generation-IV reactors and in particular of the SFRs.

The SFRs safety demonstration benefits from many positive aspects:

- the capability to remove the reactor core decay heat by natural convection, without intake of external water and with the ever-available air as the final heat sink;
- the large margin between the sodium temperature during normal operations and its boiling point;
- the favourable character of the concept towards dosimetry and environmental impact, during operation;
- the primary circuit significant thermal inertia, which provides significant grace periods before need of human intervention;

- the absence of pressurization of the primary circuit and of the secondary circuits;
- the simplicity of core operations and the absence of neutron poisons in normal operations (no xenon effect unlike thermal-spectrum reactors);
- the efficient trapping by sodium of the main fission products (in particular iodine and caesium).

On the other hand, the reactor design will have to take into account the SFRs sensitive points identified in the previous projects, and which deserve special attention, namely:

- At nominal conditions, the core is not in its most reactive configuration.
- The power density is generally high.
- A significant portion of the core may have a positive sodium void effect.
- Sodium reacts chemically with many elements, in particular with water, air and concrete, resulting in energy releases that may be significant, as well as in hydrogen production in case of reaction with water. In contact with air, the aerosols coming from a sodium fire will turn into sodium hydroxide and then into sodium carbonate, before being found relatively quickly under the form of sodium bicarbonate, completely harmless.
- The liquid sodium opacity and temperature make it difficult to inspect the structures under sodium.
- Although some components may be designed with provisions so as to facilitate interventions and replacements, these are still difficult for sodium circuits and components.
- Unloading sub-assemblies from the core lasts longer than on a water reactor.

It is proposed for ESFR-SMART to fulfil the achievement of safety objectives:

- on the one hand, by controlling the SFRs sensitive points such as the core neutron reactivity potential, the sodium chemical reactivity, the under sodium inspection;
- on the other hand, by relying upon the SFRs favourable characteristics, the plant natural behaviour and the passivity facilitated by the coolant efficiency, the grace and autonomy periods, *etc.*

In particular, as compared to PWRs, specific safety concerns of large SFRs with MOX fuel are related to reactivity insertion. In ESFR-SMART, measures addressing these concerns are introduced by taking into account earlier EU and international studies, in particular:

- passive devices for introduction of negative reactivity in case of abnormal situations (loss of coolant flow, increase of coolant temperature);
- reduction of the coolant void effect to a near-zero value to avoid significant energy release in case of coolant boiling;
- special tubes for partial relocation of molten fuel/structure from the core in order to prevent creation of a large molten fuel/structure pool in the core.

This enables to strengthen the safety demonstration robustness, for this concept. We will detail in the following chapters a list of new safety measures for the ESFR reactor, aimed to improve implementation of the three main safety functions (plus some provisions for sodium chemical reactivity control).

4. Safety measures to improve the control of the reactivity

Several measures are proposed for further studies in the ESFR-SMART R&D framework, with the goal to ensure that the core reactivity control in ESFR-SMART is even better than in CP ESFR.

New core conception with reduced sodium void effect

In order to prevent core power excursion in case of loss of flow transients, it is proposed to adopt, at the first stage, a core with a globally zero or even slightly negative sodium void effect. Depending on the results obtained, it would be possible to look at the advantages and disadvantages of a core with

improved Doppler effect. These new core conceptions may provide an even more favourable natural behaviour on most of the accidental transient sequences such as ULOF, ULOHS, UTOP, *etc.*

Passive control rod

Passive control rods are proposed as self-actuated reactivity control devices for the core. The absorber insertion into the reactor is thus passively obtained, *i.e.* without any use of instrumentation and control (I&C), when some criteria on physical parameters are met, *e.g.* low primary sodium flow rate or high primary sodium temperature.

Ultra-sonic measurements for knowledge of the core geometry

It is suggested to study the potential of ultrasonic means at the core periphery to monitor its global geometry during operations and to verify the absence of significant gaps between subassemblies (thus further preventing the risk of significant core compaction).

5. Safety measures to improve the confinement of radioactive materials

Recovery of the safety vessel functions by the reactor pit

The CP-ESFR safety vessel function was to contain the sodium in the event of the main vessel leakage, while maintaining in it a level of sodium sufficient to allow the sodium inlet into the intermediate heat exchanger (IHX) and keeping a sodium circulation for the core cooling. To recover this function by the reactor pit (hence suppressing the safety vessel), it is necessary to overlay the reactor pit with a metal-sheet liner so as to withstand the reception of a possible sodium leak and to bring it closer to the main vessel so that the volume between vessel and pit remains identical to the volume between the two vessels. This option will be studied trying to take benefit from the following anticipated advantages (see Figure 1):

- The replacement of the safety vessel by a liner with a DHR system attached, which can favour increased decay heat removal capabilities through the reactor pit.
- The simplification of the safety demonstration with respect to a potential question related to the double leak of the two vessels.
- A fault tolerant structure well adapted to the mitigation functions.
- The main vessel in-service inspection remains possible, as the main vessel still remains accessible from the reactor pit, by the top of the space between vessel and liner).

A special arrangement of the reactor pit is necessary in order to be able to operate in normal conditions, to support an accidental sodium leak of the primary vessel and to be able to cope with severe accident mitigation. It is proposed for ESFR-SMART a “mixed” steel-concrete structure for the reactor pit. A sacrificial material is provided between this “mixed structure” and the metal sheet liner. This material has to be chemically compatible with sodium and must protect the mixed structure even in case of leak through the inner sheet liner. For the liner material, an expansion coefficient is recommended as low as possible. Two independent active cooling systems will be installed in the reactor pit. The first system is an in-oil DHR circuit attached to the liner. Conversely to water, oil is able to support high temperature, but is likely to decompose in case of too high temperatures. The feasibility of implementation of an in-oil circuit close to the reactor vessel needs to be investigated both in case of normal operation and considering of all plausible accidents. Two possibilities have to be studied: this oil circuit located inside or outside of the liner. The second system is in-water active cooling circuits installed inside the concrete pit wall. This system is able to maintain the concrete temperature under 70°C in all situations, and even if the oil circuit is lost. Studies will notably be led as regards the thermomechanical constraints on the metal sheet liner in case of a main vessel leak. The sacrificial material could be, for example, an inert-to-sodium concrete (cf. the EFR Project) with moreover thermal properties (insulating and refractory material), and the metal sheet liner being a lost casing when pouring this concrete.

Figure 1. Detail of the reactor pit with reactor vessel (RV), gas gap (GG), metallic liner (ML); sacrificial material (SM), concrete (C) and decay heat removal system (DHR3) in oil attached to the liner and in water inside the concrete

Figure 2. ESFR-SMART diagrid, strongback and core catcher (green) at the reactor vessel bottom

Massive metallic roof

Superphenix experience feedback [4] leads to recommend that the roof is hot at its bottom part (so as to minimize the aerosol deposits) and has no water cooling. This last recommendation will be a key point for demonstrating the practical elimination of huge entry of water into the primary circuit. The EFR massive metallic roof is therefore taken over, which presents many other advantages such as neutron shielding and mechanical resistance. Its thickness will be defined by the industrial manufacturing contingencies, but should be about 80 cm. In the upper part, a heat insulator will eventually be installed so as to limit the heat flux to be evacuated during nominal conditions by air flow in forced convection or even natural convection.

Leak tightness of roof penetrations

It is proposed to study penetrations featuring improved leak tightness during operation with the goal to avoid (as far as possible) primary sodium leakage through the roof in case of an energetic core meltdown scenario. Such leakages would be difficult to determine, and can thus lead to very conservative overpressures in the containment, making it necessary to implement systems such as dome or polar table which are expensive, quite complex and the suppression of which could facilitate the reactor operation.

To overcome these difficulties, the following options will be studied:

- For large components, pump and heat exchanger penetrations: they are already firmly bolted for earthquake issues. It is proposed to weld a sealing shell so as to ensure the leak tightness in fast overpressure transient. These components are not intended to be frequently handled, but if this handling is required, a grinding will enable to remove them easily.
- For rotating plugs: independently of the possible inflatable seals, the leak tightness with eutectic seals, which are liquefied during the handling phases so as to enable the rotation [4, 5], is recommended. Conversely, when operating the reactor, these seals are solidified and the design retained should eventually be such that there is no leakage possibility in the case of a severe accident with energy release. The design and safety investigations will be necessary to reach this goal.
- Consistently with this strategy, to improve the primary sodium confinement in the main vessel, it is also proposed to consider:

- an integrated primary cold trap, likewise at Superphenix, so as to avoid any primary sodium circulation outside the vessel;
- a sufficiently low argon pressure in the cover gas to avoid any sodium-fountain effect of a plunging pipe.

In-vessel core catcher

The mitigation of a severe accident with core meltdown will be achieved by means of a corium receiver, also called core catcher, located at the bottom of the vessel, under the core support plate (Figure 2). Transfer tubes, coming from the core, emerge above the core catcher so as to channel the molten corium. The use, as in the Russian reactor BN 800, of molybdenum, characterized by a high fusion temperature, will notably be studied as regards its potential for avoiding melting of the core catcher structure and facilitating the power removal by conduction. The use of hafnium-type poisons will be studied as regards avoidance of any potential re-criticality. The core catcher will be designed for the whole core meltdown.

6. Safety measures to improve heat removal from the core

Hydraulic diodes

The possibility will be studied to equip the primary pump or diagrid connection with hydraulic diodes (anti reverse flow devices) enabling to limit the return flow towards a primary pump in case of spurious stopping and thus to increase the residual flow rate in the core.

Decay heat removal (DHR)

The secondary circuits are the normal power removal circuits (Figure 3). Their use for DHR in case of all primary pumps trip is very useful since that allows creating, in the IHX, a cold column essential for the establishment of a good natural convection in the primary circuit (Figure 4). The secondary circuit design (Figure 3) will be optimized so as to enable a good heat removal by air in natural convection, that is to say, in the extreme situation when both the feed water and the electrical power supply have been lost.

For this purpose, several provisions are taken:

- A loop design enabling an easy establishment of natural convection will be adopted.
- The CP ESFR design for steam generators (SGs), with six modules per loop will be kept. We will take advantage of the large exchange surface, related to the SG modular design, to have opportunities for cooling these modules by air in natural or forced convection (through hatch openings, likewise at Phenix reactor, as shown in Figure 3). This will be the heat sink for the secondary loop. We will call this system DHRS-2 (Decay Heat Removal System) or secondary DHRS (see Figure 5).
- Finally it is foreseen to add one or more thermal pumps in the secondary circuits (see a small grey cylinder on the hot leg in Figure 3). Thermal pumps are passive electromagnetic pumps using thermoelectricity provided by the difference in temperatures and with no need of external electricity supply (Figure 6). They provide the flow rate also in nominal conditions.

In addition to the secondary DHR loops, there will be two independent cooling circuits in the reactor pit, one with oil exchanger brazed on the liner and one with water inside the concrete (see red and green tubes in Figure 1), capable to maintain the whole pit at temperatures below 70°C. Suppressing the safety vessel will make these devices attached to the liner much more efficient, and should be able to assure a large part of the Decay Heat Removal, maybe 100% or close to 100% . We will call this system DHRS-3 or DHRS-Pit.

Figure 3. View of the ESFR-SMART secondary loop:
 IHX: Intermediate Heat Exchanger;
 ThP: Thermal Pump;
 SP: Secondary Pump;
 SG: modular Steam Generators

Figure 4. View of the natural convection inside the ESFR-SMART primary vessel

If the safety analysis (demonstration of practical elimination of loss of DHR function) establishes that these DHR systems are not sufficient, it is proposed to add cooling circuits by sodium/air heat exchangers connected to the IHXs piping. These circuits, which we will call DHRS-1 or primary DHRS (see Figure 5), have several advantages compared to independent systems located in the primary circuit (formerly used in the CP ESFR design):

- No additional roof penetrations are required (gain on the main vessel diameter).
- The cold column is maintained in the IHX, which is the guarantee of a good natural convection in the primary circuit through the core.
- This circuit can use the already existing purification circuit of the corresponding secondary loop and minimizes the number of sodium circuits to be managed by the operator.
- It is still available even when the secondary loop is drained.

The DHRS-1 circuit ability to operate in natural convection will be assessed together with the possible addition of a thermal pump (Figure 6) to further increase its capabilities and help for the starting of the operation.

7. Safety measures to improve control of sodium fires

As the provisions to prevent any leakage of primary sodium have already been outlined in Section 5, this chapter will only focus on the risks related to a secondary sodium leakage. In this sense, it should be noted that releases are mainly a chemical risk considering that no or very little radioactivity is present in the secondary sodium circuit. Possible impacts of sodium fires on other safety systems should also be addressed.

Figure 5. General view of ESFR-SMART primary and secondary systems

Figure 6. Thermal pump concept with permanent magnets shown in red and electrodes in grey

Figure 7. View of the double-wall piping with insulation/detection

Double wall for piping with quick sodium fire detection

All secondary sodium circulation loops are protected against leakage by a double wall piping (Figure 7). The piping itself is covered with an insulation including quick sodium fire detection. Complementary detections can be added between the two pipings, as sodium smoke detection in the partitioned interior zone. This set of provisions will be studied with regard to its potential for justifying the secondary sodium fire control and its integration in a coherent set of design options aiming at simplifying the above-roof arrangement (for example, through possible suppression of a dome or a polar table).

8. Sodium/water reaction control

Rather conventional devices enable to efficiently control this risk. Modular SGs are retained for studies, considering the possibility to quickly detect sodium water reaction, followed by the depressurisation/ isolation and draining of the faulty module. The choice of modular SG allows also minimizing the theoretical envelope accidents. In case of water/sodium reaction, the consequences on

the plant operations are limited and the operation can continue with remaining modules. Mitigation means against risk of sodium-water-air reaction will have also to be studied.

9. Severe accident mitigation

A more robust design than CP-ESFR is proposed for Severe Accident mitigation studies:

- A core catcher is provided at the bottom of the vessel, designed for the whole core meltdown (see a starting design to be further developed in Figure 2).
- Mitigation devices inside the core (corium discharge tubes) will channel the molten fuel to the core catcher.
- The re-criticality of this core should be made impossible by disposition of dedicated material such as hafnium inside the core catcher.
- The reactor pit (Figure 1) should accept sodium leakage and, with its upper thick metal roof, should form a solid, tight and that-can-be-cooled containment system.
- This corium long-term cooling will be managed by the diversified cooling measures provided in the SG and in the pit (DHRS-2 and DHRS-3).
- The use of DHRS-1 circuits may be done as a supplement so as to continue the reactor block cooling even with the three secondary circuits being drained.

10. In-service inspection

Although not yet addressed by the ESFR-SMART project, recent advances on in-sodium ultrasonic sensors and on robotics will be expected to enable inspections during periodic outages. Partial sodium draining (such as realized at Phenix) should enable visual inspections of the upper part, if required.

11. Dosimetry and releases

It is known that, during normal operations, the SFR releases are almost zero for gas. The only liquid radioactive release is the liquid used to wash fuel subassemblies or for washing and decontamination of components [4, 5]. In terms of the personnel dosimetry, this reactor design leads to a dosimetry much lower than on the water reactors [6]. This benefit will be kept for ESFR-SMART.

12. Simplicity and human factor

Starting from the CP-ESFR design [2], our approach has consisted in proposing the simplest possible reactor, while keeping the necessary lines-of-defence. It is expected that this simplicity should contribute to the whole reactor safety, by making it easier to operate. Compared to CP-ESFR, the following simplifications will be studied in that frame:

- dome (or polar table) suppression;
- safety-vessel functions taken over by the reactor pit;
- primary sodium containment improvement;
- natural convection cooling enhancement in the secondary side;
- optimized and simplified DHR dedicated circuits.

Passive and redundant systems which are independent of instrumentation and control or of the operators' action will enable the reactor reactivity control and its cooling by natural convection, even in the most severe cases of simultaneous loss of cooling water and electrical power supply. With all those improvements, the new design is then more forgiving; both with respect to the reactivity control, as well as at the intervention time required from the operator (enhanced grace period).

Conclusion

The paper gave the first ideas about possible new safety measures proposed for European Sodium Fast Reactor studies in the frame of the Horizon-2020 EU ESFR-SMART project, *e.g.*:

- Core design with improved safety parameters: special geometry and composition will significantly decrease a global void reactivity effect, enhance the prevention of severe accidents and mitigate their consequences. Three types of control rods will be considered, including active, *i.e.* automatically activated, and passive, *i.e.* activated by physical parameters, such as sodium temperature or sodium flowrate.
- Improved primary sodium confinement: The new design of the pit should be able to receive and confine the sodium leaking from the primary vessel. The level of sodium in the primary vessel in this case should remain high enough to assure natural convection through the core. A massive metallic roof above the pit assures the sodium containment even in the case of the worst severe accidents. Other measures are taken with the goal to avoid primary sodium leaks in the above roof area
- Secondary loops design efficient in natural convection: Even in case of loss of feed water in the steam generators and loss of electricity supply for the secondary pumps, the measures taken on the secondary loops will be able to assure an efficient DHR by active or passive ways. These measures will include an optimized geometry of the secondary loops to promote the natural convection of the secondary sodium, the use of fully passive thermal pumps to increase the cooling flow rate, and the use of the steam generator modules to promote the cooling of their external surfaces by convection of atmospheric air.

The proposed set of the modifications of the CP ESFR design aims at consistency with the main lines of safety evolutions for Generation-IV SFRs since the Fukushima accident, but needs, as indicated in introduction, to be validated by other tasks works during this four-year project

Acknowledgement

The work has been prepared within EU Project ESFR-SMART which has received funding from the EURATOM Research and Training Programme 2014-2018 under the Grant Agreement No. 754501.

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